

Data management

Data are the foundation upon which our knowledge is built. To answer big questions, we often need big datasets - too large for any one person, or even one project, to collect by themselves. The Nansen Legacy project has brought together a multidisciplinary team of more than 300 scientists to collect data from the northern Barents Sea, with an important aim to make all collected data be openly available. By publishing data in standardized formats with comprehensive metadata and persistent identifiers, we enhance the likelihood of data reuse and allow data usage to be tracked. The more data we publish, the faster we can progress as a scientific community.

Norwegian
Marine
Data Centre

Norwegian
Polar
Data Centre

Arctic
Data Centre

National
Infrastructure for
Research Data

Data that are published in a standardized format can be combined automatically or with minimal human effort to create a larger dataset that can be visualized online or downloaded to your computer. This is only effective at scale if data are FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

F indability

- Registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
- Assigned a persistent and globally unique identifier.
- Includes metadata to help someone find the data – e.g. where and when the data were collected.

A ccessibility

- Freely available to humans and machines.
- Authentication and authorization to use the data is allowed where necessary.
- Available online through references from discovery metadata.

I nteroperability

- Adopt standardized vocabularies (terms and descriptions that are commonly agreed upon).
- Published in a software-independent, standardized file.
- Data can be understood by a person or machine.

R eusability

- Published with a clear and accessible data usage license.
- Includes metadata that describes the data (e.g. units, descriptions) following domain-relevant community standards.

1. Convert data to a different format for downloading.

2. Visualize data from multiple files together online.

Physical data

Each depth profile is a separate CF-NetCDF

3D visualization of the data

Biodiversity data

RECOMMENDATIONS

Our world is under threat from climate change and habitat destruction. Our knowledge of what lives in the Arctic is limited, particularly in the deep sea. To improve our understanding of what impact these changes are having, we first need the data to learn what organisms live there today, how the physical environment is changing and how these organisms are being impacted by these changes.